

IMPLEMENTATION OF GUARANTEES OF RIGHTS AND LEGAL INTERESTS OF FOREIGN INVESTORS

Begmatov Akmal Mustafoevich

Republic of Uzbekistan

Law enforcement academy

Independent researcher

Abstract. In this article, as a result of the globalization of the economy, the problem of the relationship between the interests of the foreign investor and the state receiving the foreign investment appeared. A foreign investor who is a party to a civil contract should be given appropriate legal guarantees, which, in turn, are recommended to be implemented through appropriate national and international legal mechanisms.

Key words: investor, legal norms, green economy, renewal, foreign investment.

In the following years, large-scale reforms are being carried out in Uzbekistan, ensuring the openness of our national economy and creating the necessary conditions for its integration into international markets has been determined as one of the priorities of these updates.

In particular, the foreign exchange market has been liberalized, and opportunities for private investors to operate in such fields as energy, geological exploration, chemistry and petrochemicals, medicine and education have been expanded.

Revolutionary decisions were made to support private business. More than two hundred licenses and permits were canceled in this field. The tax burden of the entrepreneur is reduced, and maximum favorable conditions are created for foreign investments.

As a result, despite the difficult situation in foreign markets, the positive dynamics of economic growth has been preserved and continues. In the last 5 years, the amount of foreign investments that entered our economy has increased 10 times and amounted to almost 40 billion dollars.

pointed out that specific projects and programs have been developed for the modernization and transformation of industrial sectors, direct further investments in the rapid development of production, utility and transport infrastructure .

The fact that the head of our country has defined the priority directions for further expansion of partnership with foreign investors is, first of all, to strengthen guarantees for the protection and protection of the rights and interests of investors. At the same time, Uzbekistan strives to deepen reforms in the banking and finance sector and is open to investors' initiatives aimed at further improving this sector. One of the important directions of our country's economic policy is to reduce the state's share in the economy and expand privatization.

Today, public-private partnership mechanisms are being implemented in all sectors. This indicates that Uzbekistan has great opportunities in terms of natural resources, and foreign investors are being created wide conditions to participate in their development. Another example is the adoption and implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy. Within its framework, special attention is being paid to the active involvement of investments and technologies from abroad in digitization processes in our country. Development of "green" economy is one of them. In particular, effective measures are being taken to develop scientific and technical potential and train specialists in the field of renewable energy sources.

Foreign investments are all property, financial, and intellectual assets mobilized by foreign investors to the economy, entrepreneurship, and other activities of another state in order to achieve high income and efficiency. Foreign investment, unlike domestic investment, is a source of external financing. They are attracted to the national economy from abroad, encouraging their arrival. But not all forms of attracting foreign capital can be an external source of financing. This applies primarily to loans and debts that require repayment with interest payments. Because foreign loans and debts of international financial institutions require the repayment of fixed interest along with the principal debt after a certain period of time. There are specific differences between foreign investments and foreign loans. In this regard, the scope of risks of foreign investments and the scope of risks of foreign loans differ.

The experience of developed countries confirms that an active investment policy occupies a central place in their economic growth. Therefore, Uzbekistan's socio-economic development goals require full reflection in its investment policy.

On guarantees of the rights of foreign investors and measures to protect them", " On investment activities " and other legal documents are the legal basis for attracting and regulating foreign investments in Uzbekistan. serves.

The formation of various forms of ownership gave a great impetus to the development of investments. In connection with the emergence of different forms of ownership, the variability of capital in sectors, its flow, distribution to regions has accelerated.

Implementation of measures aimed at deepening market economy reforms, economic liberalization and strengthening the protection of property rights.

It will have a positive effect on improving the investment environment in our country and attracting foreign investments, which are increasing in volume.

In conclusion, it can be said that, based on world practice and experience,

it is no longer possible to solve the problems that hinder the investment and innovation activity of business by simple means, that is, by giving incentives or publishing new declarative norms. In order to activate private investments, it is necessary to liberalize business activities. Continuous dialogue with business, identification and overcoming of obstacles to the development of certain sectors should be carried out step by step.

Development of an investment policy strategy focused on the most promising sectors of Uzbekistan. Given that the investment environment affects all areas of activity in the country, the scope of reforms covers economic, institutional, education, health, agriculture, water supply, energy, transport and other areas.

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